

Research Article

Boosting Accounting Skills through Visual and Digital Tools: Impact on UiTM Pahang's Accounting Students

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Abstract: *This study aims to support advanced-level accounting students in preparing published financial statements for companies, facilitating a thorough understanding of the process. The methodology involves using color coding to differentiate between debits and credits, enhancing students' grasp of fundamental bookkeeping tasks. The technique was tested on 159 students, including Part 5 Diploma and Degree-level accounting students. A key challenge identified was students' difficulty in balancing accounts. To overcome this, the approach was refined by incorporating Microsoft Excel and introducing targeted balancing techniques. The findings reveal that these improvements eliminated issues with account imbalances, resulting in accurately balanced financial statements. Overall, the study demonstrated that this method enhances basic accounting skills, deepens students' comprehension of financial statements, and proves especially beneficial for students struggling with accounting concepts. Moreover, it made learning accounting more accessible, enjoyable, and easy to apply.*

Keywords: *Financial Statement Preparation; Accounting Education; Bookkeeping Techniques; Excel Integration; Student Performance Improvement.*

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's dynamic business environment, accounting professionals must demonstrate proficiency in preparing accurate financial statements, which are crucial for decision-making. In addition, as stated by Tulvinschi, M. (2019), the quality of decision also depends on the accuracy and significance of the information. Advanced-level accounting students are expected to develop the ability to prepare published financial statements that comply with regulatory standards. However, students often struggle with foundational accounting concepts, particularly in recording transactions correctly and balancing accounts. A study in South Africa by Musetha, T. C. (2022) has revealed this phenomena where students fails to do basic accounting calculations when study accounting subject. As a result,

errors accumulate and lead to inaccurate financial statements, undermining their understanding and performance in accounting courses.

This study aims to address these challenges by introducing an innovative teaching method that employs color coding for basic bookkeeping tasks, specifically in identifying debits and credits. This method simplifies the learning process by providing visual aids to categorize transactions accurately. Recognizing that balancing accounts is a persistent difficulty among students, the study also integrates Microsoft Excel and introduces specific techniques to facilitate the reconciliation and balancing of accounts.

The core objective of the study is to enhance students' basic accounting skills, improve their comprehension of financial reporting, and make the learning process engaging. A sample of 159 students—consisting of both Diploma Part 5 students and Degree-level students—was selected to participate in this study. Accounting courses often become boring and even intimidating for students because the material is often considered difficult or involves a lot of calculations (Karundeng, F., 2020). Through this research, the study seeks to assess whether these situations could be enhanced by eliminating account imbalances and ultimately make accounting education more accessible and enjoyable for students of varying skill levels.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Study Design

The study adopted a quasi-experimental design involving the implementation of color-coded bookkeeping techniques and Excel-based balancing methods. Students were divided into two groups: Diploma and Degree students. The aim was to determine the applicability of the method across academic levels and measure its impact on students with different skill sets.

2.2 Color-Coded Method

The core innovation in this study was the use of color coding for debits and credits to aid students in tracking transactions. For example, debits were assigned yellow and credits were assigned red. This visual differentiation allowed students to easily identify the two components of double-entry bookkeeping. Such a technique was expected to reduce confusion in identifying the nature of transactions and assist in proper posting.

The innovation introduced in this study builds upon the existing Eagleeyes product, a visual learning tool designed to enhance students' understanding of accounting principles through color coding. Recognizing the effectiveness of Eagle Eyes in simplifying the distinction between debits and credits, this study further advanced the approach by integrating Microsoft Excel as a supporting tool. Excel was employed to automate calculations, provide real-time feedback on account balances, and facilitate the reconciliation of transactions. This combination of visual aids and digital tools created a more interactive learning experience, helping students develop accurate bookkeeping skills and prepare balanced financial statements with greater ease.

2.3 Excel-Based Techniques

Recognizing that balancing accounts was a major obstacle, Microsoft Excel was incorporated as a supporting tool. The use of MS Excel is not something uncommon in accounting education where a study by Kelly, O., et. al (2023) suggests that the students' capability in using MS Excel would enhance

their success when entering the accountancy profession. So, in conducting our study, templates were designed to assist students with automated calculations and reconciliation techniques. These templates provided real-time feedback by indicating whether entries were properly balanced, allowing students to correct errors immediately. The Excel sheets were preformatted to help students track entries with built-in formulas for summing debits and credits, thereby reinforcing their understanding of the balancing concept.

2.4 Participants

A total of 159 students participated in the study, comprising Part 5 Diploma students and Degree-level students enrolled in advanced accounting courses. Participants were introduced to the new method during scheduled accounting classes. They were required to complete a series of exercises, including journal entries, ledger postings, and financial statement preparation, using the color-coded and Excel-based approach.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 Improved Accuracy in Financial Statements

The implementation of the color-coded and Excel-integrated method significantly improved students' ability to balance accounts. Before using these techniques, students often struggled with imbalanced trial balances and inaccurate financial statements. After the intervention, however, no major issues with account imbalances were reported. Students successfully applied the color-coded method in tracking transactions and using Excel to detect and correct errors in real time.

3.2 Enhanced Basic Accounting Skills

The study found that the students' understanding of basic accounting principles improved considerably. Both the Diploma and Degree students displayed better proficiency in recording journal entries, posting to ledgers, and preparing financial statements. This method was particularly effective in helping underperforming students, who initially faced challenges in grasping bookkeeping concepts.

3.3 Increased Student Engagement

A key outcome of the study was the increased level of student engagement. Students reported that the color-coded approach made accounting more enjoyable and less intimidating. The combination of visual aids with Excel automation provided them with a practical, hands-on learning experience. As a result, students became more motivated to complete exercises and actively participate in class discussions.

4. DISCUSSION

4.1 Effectiveness of the Color-Coded Approach

The use of color coding proved to be highly effective in simplifying complex bookkeeping tasks. Visual learning techniques have been widely recognized for their ability to enhance comprehension, and this study's findings align with previous research on the benefits of visual aids in education. By visually distinguishing between debits and credits, the method reduced cognitive load and helped students focus on the core principles of double-entry accounting.

4.2 *The Role of Excel in Learning*

The integration of Microsoft Excel was another critical factor in the success of the intervention. Excel provided students with a practical tool to track transactions, perform calculations, and detect imbalances instantly. The use of preformatted templates also enabled students to focus on conceptual understanding rather than manual calculations, which often lead to errors. This aligns with the growing trend of incorporating technology into accounting education, preparing students for professional environments where spreadsheet tools are essential.

4.3 *Addressing Performance Gaps*

The study revealed that students with poor academic performance benefited the most from the new approach. These students, who had previously struggled with traditional teaching methods, found the color-coded and Excel-based techniques easier to understand and apply. This underscores the importance of diversifying teaching strategies to accommodate students with different learning styles.

5. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study demonstrate that the color-coded and Excel-enhanced method is an effective teaching tool for improving accounting students' skills in preparing financial statements. By addressing common challenges such as imbalanced accounts and errors in transaction recording, this approach has enabled students to develop a deeper understanding of financial reporting processes. The use of color coding made accounting tasks more engaging and accessible, while the integration of Excel templates streamlined the learning process by providing real-time feedback on account balances.

This teaching method not only improved the performance of advanced-level accounting students but also proved to be particularly beneficial for underperforming students, making the learning process more inclusive. The study highlights the value of visual aids and technology in education, offering insights for accounting educators seeking to enhance student learning outcomes. Similarly, a study by Abd Rahim, et. al (2022) found that teaching accounting principal through board game using colour coding has a favourable impact on students' learning excitement and enjoyment. Additionally, Jamaluddin et al. (2027) discovered that students taught using a colour-coded gamification approach achieved higher performance compared to those taught using traditional methods.

Future research could explore the long-term impact of this approach and its potential application to other areas of accounting education. Additionally, further studies could examine how students' proficiency in using Excel influences their transition from academic environments to professional accounting roles.

In conclusion, the color-coded bookkeeping and Excel-enhanced balancing technique offers a promising solution to the challenges faced by accounting students, making the learning experience fun, practical, and effective.

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